

GCOM Data Utilization at NOAA

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ABSTRACT

The Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency's (JAXA's), Global Change Observation Mission (GCOM) will provide environmental satellite remote-sensing data for at least 13 years starting in 2011. The utilization of these data will yield great benefits for the research and operational user communities. NOAA is working collaboratively with JAXA and NASA to fully utilize the GCOM data in support its diverse operational mission which includes weather and ocean forecasting and warning, climate monitoring and prediction, fishery and marine mammal management, ocean spill response and mitigation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency's (JAXA's), Global Change Observation Mission (GCOM) will observe environmental changes on earth continuously for at least thirteen years starting in 2011. To achieve global, comprehensive long-term, and homogeneous observations, GCOM consists of two satellite types, GCOM-W (Water) and GCOM-C (Climate). The GCOM-W1 satellite will carry the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-2 (AMSR-2) and the GCOM-C1 satellite will carry the Second-generation Global Imager (SGLI). Additionally, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), working with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), is exploring the possibility of providing a Dual-Frequency Scatterometer (DFS) for the GCOM-W2 and W3 satellites. Using environmental satellites to observe the earth from space is one of the key tools in forecasting weather, analyzing climate, and monitoring hazards worldwide. This 24-hour global coverage provides us with a continuous stream of information critical for making decisions affecting everything from what you are going to wear today to governments making decisions about how to deal with climate change.

2. GCOM-W

The GCOM mission will provide global observations important to weather forecasting and warnings, and ocean and climate monitoring, modeling and research. GCOM-

W1 will carry the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer (AMSR) – 2), which is follow-on to the highly successful AMSR-E sensor aboard NASA's Aqua mission. The GCOM-W1 (currently scheduled to be launched in Fiscal year 2012) will observe precipitation, water vapor amounts, wind speed above the ocean, sea water temperatures (Fig. 1), soil moisture and snow cover. GCOM-W1 data will provide an important gap-filler to permit microwave radiometer data continuity between the termination of the NASA Aqua mission which was launched in May 2002 with a design life of 5 years, and the launch of the NPOESS C-2 spacecraft in 2016 containing the Microwave Imager/Sounder (MIS) sensor.

3. GCOM-C

GCOM-C will carry a multi-wavelength optical radiometer (Second Generation Global Imager – SGLI). The GCOM-C1 (currently scheduled to be launched in Fiscal Year 2013) will observe clouds, aerosol, seawater color (Ocean Color), vegetation, snow and ice. Normalized water leaving radiances from SGLI will be used to generate additional parameters such as chlorophyll concentration, total suspended matter, colored dissolved organic matter, primary productivity and true color imagery. These products will be used to produce harmful algal bloom forecasts (Fig. 1), integrated ecosystem assessments, water quality assessments, ocean acidification/carbon flux studies. GCOM-C1 data will compliment the data provided by the Visible Infrared Imager Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) on NPOESS to support ocean color and climate-related requirements. The SGLI data will provide additional coverage by filling the NPOESS observation gap in the morning orbit.

Gulf of Mexico Harmful Algal Bloom Bulletin
 Region: South Florida
 4 August 2008
 NOAA Ocean Service
 NOAA Satellite and Information Service
 Last bulletin: July 28, 2008

Satellite chlorophyll image with possible HAB areas shown by red polygons. Cell concentration sampling data from July 25 to 31 shows as red (high), orange (medium), yellow (low), brown (low at bluewater) low by, purple (very low at), pink (present), and green (not present). For a list of cell count data providers and a key to the cell concentration categories, please see the HABHS bulletin guide: http://www.csc.noaa.gov/csr/hab/habhs_bulletin_guide.pdf

Please note the following restrictions on all SeaWiFS imagery derived from CoastWatch:
 1. Data are restricted to civil marine applications only, i.e. federal, state, and local government use/distribution is permitted.
 2. Image products may be published in newspapers. Any other publishing arrangements must receive CoastWatch approval via the CoastWatch Program.

Conditions Report

There is currently no indication of a harmful algal bloom at the coast in southwest Florida. No impacts are expected alongshore southwest Florida today through Sunday, August 10.

Analysis

There is currently no indication of a harmful algal bloom at the coast in southwest Florida. No *Karenia brevis* was found in samples collected last week between Pinellas County and the Florida Keys (FWRI MML, SCBD, 7/30-8/1). Cloud cover has obscured recent satellite imagery, limiting analysis. Imagery from July 31 continued to show patches of elevated to high chlorophyll alongshore SW Florida due to confirmed non-harmful algae. Dead fish have been reported in the upper Tampa Bay, but are not due to *K. brevis* (FWRI, 08/01). Upwelling conditions are possible through Wednesday, August 6, however bloom formation alongshore is unlikely. No impacts are expected along the coast through Sunday, August 10.

Please note that SeaWiFS imagery is temporarily unavailable for display on this bulletin due to technical difficulties; MODIS imagery is shown on pages 1 and 2 of this bulletin.

Wenstermacher, Fisher

Wind speed and direction are averaged over 12 hours from buoy measurements. Length of line indicates speed; angle indicates direction. Red indicates that the wind direction favors upwelling near the coast. Values to the left of the dotted vertical line are measured values; values to the right are forecasts.

Wind Analysis

SW Florida: Southeast to easterly winds today through Wednesday, with onshore winds in the afternoon (5-10 kts; 3-5 m/s). Southwesterlies Thursday and Friday (5-10 kts; 3-5 m/s)

To see previous bulletins and forecasts for other Harmful Algal Bloom Bulletin regions, visit the NOAA CoastWatch bulletin archive: <http://coastwatch.noaa.gov/hab/bulbs.htm>

Figure 1 Example of algal bloom forecast product produced by the NOAA CoastWatch project.

http://coastwatch.noaa.gov/hab/bulletins_ms.htm

4. IMPACT ON NOAA OPERATIONS

The GCOM satellites will provide comprehensive observations of the surface layer of the Earth such as the atmosphere, including clouds, land, oceans and the critical sea ice concentrations of the Northern and Southern hemispheres. The data from the GCOM mission will provide critical meteorological, oceanographic, climate and environmental observation data for NOAA to be used for monitoring, modeling, forecasting and research of the atmosphere, oceans and climate. The NWS will use the data to improve forecasting and warning products and services. National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) will use the sea surface temperature and ocean color data for ocean productivity and biological activity studies and to gain a greater understanding of marine habitat (Figure 2). National Ocean Service (NOS) will use the ocean color data to aid in the detection of harmful algal blooms along the coastline. Another example of how data from GCOM would be utilized by NOAA is shown in Figure 3 which blends true color imagery and satellite ocean surface vector wind data over the Deep Horizon oil spill area. In this case the merging of satellite wind and imagery data would aid in deployment and safety decisions concerning spill mitigation assets and provide input to oil spill trajectory/dispersion forecasts. This data will also provide continuity to the climate data records started by AMSR-E and MODIS on the NASA Aqua mission.

GCOM cooperation directly contributes to the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) Disaster, Water, Weather and Climate Societal Benefit Areas (SBA) by providing critical meteorological, climate and environmental observation data. The cooperation also will contribute indirectly to the other SBAs of Health, Energy, Ecosystem, Agriculture, and Biodiversity. GCOM-W will provide continuity of oceanographic and maritime meteorological data currently provide by NASA's Aqua satellite. These measurements have proven valuable for numerical weather prediction in areas over the open oceans which subsequently impact medium to long range weather forecasting in coastal regions. Precipitation data from this instrument will aid forecasting of major storm systems threatening human safety, and damage to coastal infrastructures. GCOM-C will provide additional advanced Visible and Infra-Red Imaging capability which will supplement coverage from the NPP and JSS spacecraft resulting in a more complete balanced nominal coverage approximately every 4-hours. This high resolution data provides faster identification of hazardous weather conditions, smoke, and volcanic ash due to the increased 4 hourly imaging coverage of a geographic area with the addition of GCOM-C versus having an 8 hour gap with only NPP and NPOESS. In addition, oceanographic benefits include improved ocean current analysis and forecast, fine scale ocean color, turbidity, and sea state. Both of these global microwave imaging/ sounding data and high resolution Vis/IR imaging capabilities have been identified by the National Academies of Science Decadal Survey as

critical to our understanding of the ocean-atmosphere interactions driving global climate change.

Figure 2 Example of sea surface temperature (left panel) and chlorophyll (right panel) retrievals overlaid with loggerhead turtle tracks (black line) along the Transitional Zone Chlorophyll Front (TZCF) in the N. Pacific during Feb. '01. The TZCF is an important foraging ground for a number of commercial and protected species. Interannual variability in its location has been tied to the reproductive success of endangered monk seal pups. (Polovina et al 2004):

Figure 3 True color image from MERIS and ocean surface vector winds from ASCAT over the Gulf of Mexico oil spill region on May 24, 2010. The winds are color-coded using the following scale blue < 2 m/s, yellow 2-3.5 m/s, orange 3.5-5 m/s and red > 5 m/s. (Image courtesy of the NOAA CoastWatch program.)

5. REFERENCES

[1] National Research Council, 2007: Earth Science and Applications from Space: National Imperatives for the Next Decade and Beyond. Pp. 456 The National Academies Press. Available online at:
http://www.nap.edu/catalog.php?record_id=11820#toc

[2] POLIVINA, J.J., BALAZS, G.H., HOWELL, E.A., PARKER, D.M., SEKI, M.P. and P.H. DUTTON. 2004. Forage and migration habitat of Loggerhead (*Caretta caretta*) and Olive Ridley (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) Turtles in the central North Pacific Ocean. Fisheries and Oceanography 13: 36–51.